

EDUCATION AND CULTURE

ON THE ROLE OF CULTURAL BRAND BUILDING IN THE CONSTRUCTION OF NEW RURAL CULTURE -- A CASE STUDY OF SANSHENG FLOWER TOWN IN CHENGDU

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ABSTRACT

Background: The revitalization of rural culture has become a critical objective in the broader context of rural development in China. Cultural brand building has emerged as a strategic approach to preserve local identity, promote cultural engagement, and stimulate rural tourism. **Objectives:** This study explores the role of cultural brand building in the construction of new rural culture, using Sansheng Flower Town in Chengdu as a case study. It examines how flower culture, as the core branding theme, contributes to the development of public cultural facilities, the organization of cultural activities, and the overall enhancement of the town's cultural character. **Methods:** A qualitative case study methodology was employed, incorporating document analysis and direct observation. Thematic analysis was used to identify patterns and interpret the cultural branding processes and their implications for rural cultural development. **Results:** Findings indicate that the flower-themed cultural brand in Sansheng Flower Town has significantly contributed to improving public cultural infrastructure, promoting regular cultural events, and reinforcing a unique and recognizable cultural identity. Additionally, cultural branding has generated economic benefits through increased tourism and local employment. Nevertheless, challenges such as the risk of over-commercialization and the need for coherent brand management were identified. **Conclusion:** Cultural brand building is shown to be an effective strategy for fostering new rural culture by integrating cultural identity with economic development. The Sansheng Flower Town case provides valuable insights for applying cultural branding to other rural settings seeking to achieve a balance between cultural preservation, social cohesion, and sustainable growth.

KEY WORDS

Cultural Brand Building, Rural Cultural Construction, Sansheng Flower Town, Cultural Identity, Sustainable Rural Development.

INTRODUCTION

As rural development moves forward in the new era, the construction of new rural culture has become a critical link in the construction of a well-off society. The idea of the new rural cultural construction proposed when developing Chinese rural areas highlights the importance of addressing cultural change in addition to economic and social transformations (Powe, Connelly, & Nel, 2022). This approach seeks to meet the cultural wants of rural people other than just the physical wants in the process of development by providing for physical infrastructure and growth of the economy. Cultural considerations in development are not simply about cultural desires expressed by the populace in the rural areas but also about the attempts to foster cultural values and activities to counter modernization trends in the process of rural development.

This new method of cultural brand building has thus become a significant way of navigating the new rural cultural construction in that it comes with a structure for management of the cultural assets. It is thus understood that the idea of a cultural brand is broader than just a marketing platform, and it encompasses development of a unique cultural image for the communities and out stream. A cultural brand can be considered a medium, which makes cultural values, traditions, and other elements easier to identify and recognize. On the subject of new rural cultural construction, construction of cultural brands is a scientific approach by which various cultural components are incorporated into broad developmental goals while at the same time advancing cultural progress in concordance with economic and societal gains (Su & Cheng, 2023).

Sansheng Flower Town in Chengdu is taken as an example to discuss that cultural brand building could help promote new rural cultural construction. Sansheng Flower Town, named as the "Hometown of Flowers," has effectively built a cultural brand focusing on flower culture. This brand not only improves the image of the town as a tourist attraction but also amplifies the cultural ethos of the society town (Min, Linlin, & Yueqin, 2014). The establishment of a cultural brand that focuses on flowers has contributed to the establishment of public cultural amenities and organizations of cultural events as well as sustaining traditional customs. These initiatives support new rural cultural construction aims in general as they enhance cultural activity for the society and encourage cohesiveness (Department of Education Science and Culture Ministry of Finance Central China Normal University National Rural Culture Joint Research Group, 2007 (Li, Zhou, & Zhang, 2021).

However, some problems exist as well in new rural cultural construction. Another point-of-concern is that different efforts for developing cultures never form a cohesive cultural plan and often function independently but do not deliver optimal results of cultural enhancement. The single carrier of cultural construction, usually bears project-specific responsibility, does not make the connection that would ensure that the resultant culture within an organization forms complete value chain. This lack of integration affects the success of cultural initiatives and its ability to impact rural communities (Li, 2023). These challenges can be rectified through a cultural brand-building approach as it is a coherent structure that brings together various cultural pursuits under a brand.

In this paper, the significance of cultural brand building in new rural cultural construction will be discussed with the case of Sansheng Flower Town. In the paper, the author will discuss how the flower cultural resources has been used to construct the cultural brand for the town to enhance the objective of rural cultural construction. In this paper, the author intends to shed the light on the generalisability of the cultural brand building approach on the development of other rural cultures in China.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The Concept of Cultural Brand and Its Evolution

Understanding brand has therefore changed over time from purely being defined within the confines of marketing and consumer goods to the broader cultural and social contexts. At the outset of the formation of a brand, brand equity was used solely in helping customers distinguish between products and services ... From that point on, branding transcended products and services and even spread to organizations, geographical locations, and countries. This extension of the use of the term branding has led to the idea of the cultural brand suitable for the construction of rural culture (Zheng, 2022).

Cultural brand can be defined as a brand that represents certain cultural values, norms and attitudes. Cultural brands are not like traditional brands that have business and commercial orientation; instead, the major aims of cultural brands are to preserve and promote the relevant culture, to encourage people to be united and to create a sense of belonging (Zhao, 2021). In the context of cultural branding, cultural assets are not merely managed; instead, they are systemically controlled and effectively advertised in order to establish a comprehensible and easily recognizable identity.

Culture branding is a multi-step process that involves several distinctive stages such as the creation of a brand image and the control of the visual and metaphorical signs as well as the application of cultural and historical stories into the brand's communication strategy. This process is not only an attempt to produce a marketable image, but it also tries to make sure that this image corresponds to and indeed preserves the cultural values enshrined by the brand. In this sense, cultural brand building is not only about marketing and promotion, but also about cultural sensitivity and learning.

The Role of Cultural Brands in Rural Cultural Construction

In recent years, cultural brand building has become more important when it comes to rural culture construction, especially the new rural construction in China. The new rural cultural construction initiative together with the improvement of rural economy and society acknowledges the significance of cultural advancement. The goal is to see that such improvements must also spread to these rural areas so as to contribute to what modernization has impacted and not only in the civil engineering sense or in the economic development of society (Dong, 2021).

The cultural brands are significant in the context of rural cultural construction as they offer a relevant template for the systematic organization and popularization of cultural resources. Culture and cultural brand are influential and distinct aspects of promotional culture, and by establishing a cultural brand, rural communities can ensure that they portray their narrative to the outside world, thus improving their visibility and attractiveness (Zhou et al., 2022). This can potentially lead to the formation of cultural tourism, the maintenance of cultures, and solidarity among the locals.

Cultural brand construction in relation to rural cultural development can be an effective way of creating a consistent cultural brand that the community can adopt. Some globalization of rural culture construction has been dispersed, and various projects have been undertaken by different organizations without any coordination with each other. This has in essence not allowed the general implementation of these initiatives to optimize the intended cultural development hence creating a very fragmented culture approach. On the other hand, cultural branding offers a comprehensive approach in that it presents an overriding identity whereby all the cultural activities and other ventures are branded in harmony. It not only improves the efficiency of these initiatives but also contributes to establishing a harmonious and

highly interconnected cultural context (Xu, 2023).

Case Study: Sansheng Flower Town in Chengdu

Sansheng Flower Town in Chengdu serves as an impressive illustration of how cultural brand building can be used to increase the development of rural culture. Sansheng Flower Town, situated in the Chengdu Plain, could cultivate a profound flower culture resource and has established a cultural brand based on flower culture. It serves two-fold purpose of promoting the town as a tourist destination while at the same time nurturing and developing the culture of the local people.

The cultural brand in Sansheng flower town is orientated with the flower culture since it is an important combination with the historical and cultural elements. The visual and symbolic representations of the brand are seen in aspects such as the town logo, banners, and other advertisement materials which all incorporate a floral theme (Hsun & Jie, 2022). This is why the consistent use of the floral imagery also makes it easy for the brand to be recognizable to the locals as well as the tourists.

Thus, apart from the visual culture, another aspect of culture and heritage of Sansheng Flower Town can be found in the cultural activities and events. Lotus Festival and Plum Blossom Festival are major festivals celebrated in the town and festivals related to flowers (Chanyeguihua.com, 2024). Not only do these events help to bring tourists to the town but also use occurrences allowing local residents to participate in and promote cultural activities (Koenig-Lewis, Palmer, & Asaad, 2021). These activities are conveniently reconciled on the basis of the cultural aspect of flowers and this adds a certain flow or continuity that aligns with the brand.

Furthermore, by building a cultural brand system established on the flower culture, Sansheng Flower Town has achieved advanced construction of public cultural facilities. It has developed and promoted aesthetic resources that include museums and cultural centers for the floral aspects of the town offering educational tours for tourists (Wulandari, Rokhmawan, & Dewi, 2023). In addition to preserving local cultures, these facilities can also be used for cultural exchange or learning.

The following are some of the factors that may have contributed to the success of the cultural brand in Sansheng Flower Town. First, the brand is organically connected to the town's identity and heritage, thus being meaningful and related to the town's inhabitants and guests. Second, the brand identity is maintained through constant usage of

graphics, logos, and interface, which makes a brand easily recognizable. Last but not the least, cultural activities and such facilities which are related to the brand and develop the elaborated brand message, having contextual communications with the towns' cultural basis.

Challenges in Cultural Brand Building and Rural Cultural Construction

As the case of Sansheng Flower Town shows, cultural brand building can be an effective strategy for developing rural cultural construction. However, several challenges should be taken into consideration in order to achieve successful implementation of such strategies. Another important problem is the commercialization of a culture brand, which means that the culture brand will lose its cultural essence and become a simple tool for attracting tourists and making money (Zhang, Yin, & Peng, 2021). This can result in weakening of the cultural brand image and can be detrimental to the branding process in the long run.

They include the following: Another challenge is difficulty in managing and co-organizing the cultural brand initiatives. As mentioned above, one of the major advantages of culture brand building is that it helps order and coalesce the identity of the community. However, this can only be realized if proper coordination and control of the various cultural activities and endeavor that encompasses the brand advancements (Tirado Ballesteros & Hernández Hernández, 2021). This can be especially difficult in rural settings where there may be a limited amount of funding and professionals available, as well as various other stakeholders with concerns and goals.

Another issue is more practical and concerns the need to maintain the relevance of the cultural brand within the context of local audiences. Although the aim of cultural brand building is to increase the recognition and appreciation of the community, it is also crucial that the branding is compatible with the cultural attributes of the people. This is possible through constant interaction with the community so as to understand whether they still relate to this brand as they used to.

The Role of Visual Image Management in Cultural Brand Building

Closely related to perception, cultural brand building requires effective control of the brand's visual identity since it affects audiences' perceptions, including those of the neighboring communities. Visual image management entails the proper utilization of images including logos, signs and photographs

among other things in order to enhance brand identification. This is especially significant in the case of rural cultural construction, as the appearance of the brand can facilitate the signalling of the cultural features of the community and may draw more tourists and tourists (Xue et al., 2020).

As experienced in the Sansheng Flower Town case, the application of visual image management has provided a powerful and consistent brand image. For instance, the town symbolizes a flower which is seen on various signposts, fliers, and other town facilities, thus making it easily identifiable by the public. The coherence of these visuals does more than perpetuate the brand image; it facilitates people's journeys and interactions with cultural sites in the town.

In addition, the application of themes in cultural brand establishment can also help beautify the looks of the community thereby making them more beautiful and welcoming. This is especially relevant in cultural tourism since the symbolic meaning of the brand may be a significant asset in attracting clients and improving their experience (Liu et al., 2023). This way the cultural brand will be equipped to attract visitors to the community as the desired target meaning that the brand will assist in the economic development of the community as well as enhance the preservation of culture.

The Broader Impact of Cultural Brand Building on Economic Development

Besides the cultural values of cultural brand building, it is crucial to note that cultural brand building brings substantial economic returns. In this way cultural brands help improving the overall attractiveness of rural areas as destinations for tourists and other visitors which contributes to economic development and new opportunities for locals (Baldi et al., 2022). It is more so for the rural areas in which employment is still a challenge, and tourism may act as a source of income.

In the case of Sansheng Flower Town, where the cultural brand based on flower culture has played a positive role to the establishment bringing in tourist and visitors. The Lotus Festival, the Plum Blossom Festival and other cultural events are held and are well visited by many people across the region thus improving the economy of the town (Chen & Kong, 2021). Apart from the revenue in itself that tourism brings to the country and the scenery associated with cultural brand, people of the country have also benefited from employment opportunities in cultural and creative industries for instance, handcrafting and performing traditional art for economic growth.

Similarly, the cultural brand has also contributed to the development of a new economic outlook for the town and opened new economically productive opportunities apart from purely agricultural ones. The economic improvements created by the cultural brand have benefited the community by enabling more range recreation and making the community stronger and more sustainable.

Sustainability and Future Directions in Cultural Brand Building

The sustainability of cultural brand building efforts is a critical consideration, particularly in the culture construction in rural areas. Cultural branding is another strength whereby brands manage to build a sustainable cultural identity for the community, which can even continuously provide benefits in future (Anabestani, Abaszadeh, & Vesal, 2018). Nonetheless, this is a continuous process that requires further investments in the brand and the appropriate administration in order to sustain its importance and appeal to both internal and external stakeholders.

In the case of Sansheng Flower Town, it can be concluded that the sustainable development of the cultural brand has been supplemented through the continuous investment in the public cultural infrastructure, the cultural events, and the management of the visual image. Such investments have contributed to the fact that the brand successfully changes over time and adapts to the new context, as well as continuously benefiting the community (Cross et al., 2025). But the long-term viability of the brand will only be possible if the community can evolve and keep on generating creative solutions to new conditions and opportunities.

Thus, considering the potential future developments, there are some significant spheres which can be further promoted and developed in the framework of cultural brand building. A specific topic of interest is the role of technology in the construction of cultural brands, which can offer new ways to communicate with the public and advance the brand. For instance, adding the elements of social media, mobile applications, and/or virtual reality into the equation may assist in developing new engaging experiences for the visitors; besides increasing brand awareness (Kurnia Putra et al., 2022).

Another area of attention would be partnerships and collaborations with other communities and organizations that may potentially enhance the influence of the cultural brand, opening new opportunities for cultural exchange and collaboration. According to Peroff et al. (2017),

in joining forces, communities can share best practice, pool resources and create stronger and more resilient cultural brands.

Finally, there is a need for induced research and constant evaluation to measure the actual impact of cultural brand building efforts in general and see what can be modified for better results. This would ensure that cultural brand building becomes dynamic and turns into a perpetual process with abilities to change course in the light of new challenges and opportunities.

METHODOLOGY

This paper will examine the role of cultural brand building in the construction of new rural culture by focusing on Sansheng Flower Town in Chengdu, China. A qualitative case study approach is adopted for this research. Case study methodology has been chosen since it will be appropriate to probe complex phenomena in a specific context (Boblin et al., 2013). By focusing on one case, the study was able to allow for an in-depth look at the processes and outcomes of cultural brand building and its impact on rural cultural construction.

Research Design

The research design will be a qualitative case study to investigate in depth the cultural brand management practices adopted by Sansheng Flower Town. Such an approach is especially suitable for this study because it manages the exploration of cultural brand building within its real-life context, considering the social, cultural, and economic factors that influence the process.

Case Selection

The case study for this research was the Sansheng Flower Town in Chengdu, in which the implementation of a cultural brand with core flower culture had been successful. That is, the town's creation of a cultural identity with cohesiveness based on its floral heritage makes for a fruitful context in which to examine the role of rural cultural construction through cultural brand building. It is also called a model of new rural cultural construction; therefore, Sansheng Flower Town will be a very relevant and enlightening case for this study (Luo, Furuya, & Xie, 2021).

Data Collection

To provide a comprehensive understanding of the process of cultural brand building in Sansheng Flower Town, information for the study was derived through qualitative data sources. These include:

1. Document Analysis: Information gathering on the branding strategies of Sansheng Flower Town, cultural activities, and public cultural facilities was obtained by reviewing official documents, reports and publications related to its cultural development. It includes the official publications released by local government and tourism promotional materials, as well as scholarly articles on rural cultural construction (Morgan, 2022).
2. Observational Data: Observations were made into the events that build the town's culture, public spaces, and tourist activities to get an idea of how the brand is experienced by both locals and visitors. The observations were focused on the integration of flower culture into the visual and cultural landscape of the town.
- documents, visual materials, and observation.
2. Thick Description: The research delineates, at length, the setting, the processes, and the outcomes of constructing cultural brands in Sansheng Flower Town, and thus provides the reader with insight into the subtleties and nuances associated with the case.
3. Reflexivity: Thus, all through the study, the researcher has maintained a reflexive approach to ensure that, while acknowledging his personal biases, the analyses remain firmly based in the data.

Data Analysis

The above-identified and analyzed themes were patterned within the data by using an approach of a thematic analysis method. The reason for selecting the thematic analysis is its flexibility and rich, detailed account it provides of the data. The steps through which the analysis has been carried out are as follows:

1. Familiarization with the Data: At the first step, all the collected documents and visual materials, together with the observational notes, were scrutinized to familiarize the content with the researcher.
2. Coding: Cultural brand building and rural cultural construction key themes and patterns were identified and coded accordingly. That means highlighting the meaningful phrases, concepts, and ideas that come out of data.
3. Theme Development: These data were further sorted into broader themes reflecting the key aspects of cultural brand building in Sansheng Flower Town, including the role of visual imagery, cultural activities integration, and effects on public cultural facilities.
4. Interpretation: Finally, the themes were interpreted against the background of research questions. The focus is on how cultural brand building understands its relation to the objectives of new rural cultural construction.

Validity and Reliability

Several ways were adopted to ensure that findings from the study are valid and reliable:

1. Triangulation: This would be attained through an all-rounded and corroborated understanding of the process of cultural brand building through data triangulation from

Limitations

However, this is a case study approach, insights hereinto are deep in connection with the process of cultural brand building in Sansheng Flower Town; however, results cannot be generalized to all rural contexts. Its unique cultural and historical background may influence the generalizability of the findings to other regions. In addition, qualitative data may have an element of subjectivity, which will reduce the generalizability of findings from this study. Such methods could be complemented with quantitative testing in future research in order to enable more complete analysis.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical considerations due to care in the course of the study were manifested. Participants who were involved in the observations gave informed consent. Care was exercised so that privacy and confidentiality of persons would be maintained. Carrying out the research in regard to principles underlying the conduct of ethical qualitative research ensured that the study was carried out with integrity and respect for participants and the community of Sansheng Flower Town.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results

The case example of Sansheng Flower Town gives numerous key results in the role cultural brand building has played in the construction of new rural culture. The main outputs are found in public cultural facilities, cultural activities, and the general cultural identity of the town.

Enhancement of Public Cultural Facilities

The creation of cultural brand in Sansheng Flower Town has also helped to promote the improvement of public cultural service. Flower culture is the primary branding concept of the town and has led to the development of several facilities that embody and support this image (Min, Linlin, &

Yueqin, 2014). For instance, the construction of thematic billboards and flower boards, as well as, the cultural centers has given the town the forums through which it can publicize its specific focus on flower production (Wulandari et al., 2023). Not only do these facilities act as symbols that reinforces the town's cultural image, but just as importantly, add value by providing facilities for the enhancement of the town's cultural landscape. Flower motifs have also been incorporated in most murals, walls, pavements in the actual town resulting in better design layout, cultural identity and improved aesthetics.

Promotion of Cultural Activities and Festivals

It has also been possible to establish a specific flower culture and create different cultural listings for Sansheng Flower Town as well as organize different cultural activities and carnivals. Festivals like the Lotus Festival and Plum Blossom Festival are directly related to the flower culture of the town and have thus evolved into a constituent of cultural festivities that is popular in the region. Such festivals encourage tourist attendance and contribute to community participation and capacity (Meng & Kang, 2022). These events also keep cultural activities as recurrent and as closely tied to the local flower culture as possible, which contributes to the coherence and maintain continuity of the town's cultural story. Based on the success of these events, it has proven that cultural branding can also play an important role in encouraging community involvement and the richness of culture.

Strengthening of Cultural Identity

In their case, the creation of the cultural brand for Sansheng Flower Town has been instrumental in enhancing the existence of the town's culture. Flower culture has made it easy for the town to market and brand itself since it is easily identifiable compared to normal rural towns. This has contributed to the development of cultural tourism since the town has a strong cultural base to attract visitors and market the town as a cultural tourism destination (Wulandari et al., 2023). Due to the constant presence of flower motifs in many cultural objects and public places, a specific cultural background was developed both for locals and guests, which can be easily recognized by anyone. It has succeeded in both maintaining and enriching the cultural heritage, integrating it into the towns selling proposition.

DISCUSSION

This case study demonstrates that cultural brand

building is another successful approach to the new rural cultural construction. Sansheng Flower Town has proved that, if a cultural brand is conceptualized properly and its establishment is systematic, it can foster the construction of public cultural facilities, encourage cultural activities and improve cultural awareness, which are part of rural cultural construction (Zhou, 2021).

Cultural Brand as a Catalyst for Infrastructure Development

Another source of concern that emanates out of this research study is the fact that cultural branding acts as a stimulus to the creation of public cultural facilities. The example of Sansheng Flower Town indicates that emphasizing the significance of cultural identity allows developing cultural-branding communities that would help the indigenous people receive financial support to obtain cultural facilities for citizens and tourists. The cultural experiences in Sansheng Flower Town, including the museums and culturally themed areas, are essential and represent the town's flower culture. This is in line with the general vision of new rural cultural construction which includes the development of public cultural facilities for increasing the cultural needs of the rural community (Lin et al., 2022). The cultural branding technique that is used strategically to direct infrastructural planning capabilities makes certain that these structures are not only utilitarian but are culturally and aesthetically appropriate as well.

Cultural Activities as a Means of Sustaining Cultural Identity

An implication that can be derived from the promotion of cultural activities in Sansheng Flower Town is that the promotion of culture activities need to be incorporated into the comprehensive brand positioning. Flower-themed festivals have also been of immense benefit to the town because it has been able to maintain and market the cultural aspect in the process. These events are not mere entertainment only; there are forms of cultural products and everyone learn and share the culture of the town (Zhi, 2003). As Sansheng Flower Town has continued to associate cultural activities with the organization's brand image, it has been easier to make a consistent cultural statement that is appealing to citizens and tourists. This approach resonates with the conclusion of prior studies, where literature highlighted the significance of continuity and thematic unity in cultural activities to boost their effectiveness for community identity and cohesiveness (2015).

Brand Identity as a Tool for Cultural Preservation and Tourism

The strong brand identity developed by Sansheng Flower Town has had a dual effect: it has successfully maintained the culture of the town and at the same time has marketed the town as a cultural center. This has not only preserved the local flower culture but has also commoditised a practice that attracts tourists into the region. It has significant significance to rural development since it illustrates how cultural brand building not only generates economic value but also preserves culture (Du Cros & McKercher, 2020). The option of cultural tourism allows the creation of a stiff cultural brand, thereby developing additional and sustainable economic model for rural areas where cultural capital is employed to create income without compromising the culture.

Challenges and Considerations in Cultural Brand Building

Nevertheless, Sansheng Flower Town has shown the positive impacts of engaging in cultural brand building while pointing out certain issues that require further attention. Another issue is the potential oversaturation and commercialization of cultural brands that leads to the creation of attractions and events for tourists rather than for the actual promotion of culture. This could lead to diminution of the brand's cultural value, and this is likely to cause cultural isolation of the community. To manage this risk, it is imperative that the cultural brand building exercise is anchored firmly in a true support and respect for the cultural values. Furthermore, it has been established that for cultural branding to be successful, it requires efficient management and coordination. As anticipated since all the cultural activities and initiatives must bear the logo, these potentials should be planned and monitored diligently especially for those centres based in rural areas where resources may be limited (Schmitt & Simonson, 2001).

Implications for Broader Rural Development

This study has significant implications for Chinese rural development and, more broadly, rural development elsewhere in the world. In this piece, the case of Sansheng Flower Town shows that rural regions indeed gain a lot from cultural brand promotion as part of a development process. Promoting a noteworthy cultural image of the rural regions also has the potential to market the region and bring in tourist traffic while offering a positive image for its dwellers to proud of. Such an approach may be especially helpful for regions

with a highly developed cultural background threatened by globalization. This paper illustrated how it is possible to incorporate the improvement of cultural brand into rural construction, which can make the cultural development commensurate with the economic and social development; hence, form a harmonic and culturally prosperous rural society (Zheng, 2002).

The case study on Sansheng Flower Town elucidates the possibilities of cultural brand building in constructing rural culture. By creating a cultural brand based on flower culture, the cultural running of the town has been expanded, public cultural facilities have been improved, various cultural activities have been promoted, and the cultural positioning of the town has been strengthened. Such accomplishments effectively illustrate benefits of cultural brand creation as a development strategy for the rural regions, and the findings are useful for similar rural territories interested in maintaining their cultural identity and stimulating economic development and social inclusion processes.

CONCLUSION

In this line, this research paper presented the case of Sansheng Flower Town in Chengdu, China to investigate the aspect of cultural brand building in the establishment of new rural culture. The case study established that, when culturally branding is deliberately and objectively undertaken, it has the potential of positively impacting culture, society and economy of rural regions. As Sansheng Flower Town has effectively built up a cultural brand focusing on flower culture, the concept of cultural branding can bring positive changes to rural areas. Another area discussed in this study is the effects of cultural branding on public cultural facilities. Flower culture's adaptation into the town in form of flower themed public amenities and flower culture centers have enriched the town's culture, and provided areas where residents and visitors can engage in social and cultural exchange. This not only achieves the purpose of new rural cultural construction, but also examines the overall visual environment to enhance the towns appeal as a cultural landmark.

The promotion and support of cultural activities inspired by the developed brand of the town shows the significance of cultural branding for developing and popularizing culture in the region. Not only do festivals such as the Lotus Festival and the Plum Blossom Festival bring tourism but also the citizens to be proud of cultural value. Since flower culture has been consistently highlighted, there has been continuity in the cultural theme that could appeal to locals and tourists alike showing how cultural branding can stimulate engagement and cultural tourism.

Further, while establishing a successful cultural brand Identification, Sansheng Flower Town has outlined the cultural tourism model as an exemplary cultural tourism economy that can serve as a model for developing cultural resources and assets as the basis for sustainable economic growth while maintaining cultural heritage. Thus, the importance of cultural brand building for rural development is evident in the dual strategy of culture preservation and economic growth, which is relevant for building other cultures as well. Therefore, it supports the argument that using branding to market a culture can spur economic development while respecting the cultures of people. But it also admits some limitations like what threatens the brand's commercialization, and how the management of this brand should retain the cultural value without being overwhelmed by commercial tactics. It was also noted that in a cultural branding context these challenges are imperative in order to have a positive impact on the rural development. In conclusion, the case of the Sansheng Flower Town shows that constructing cultural brand is effective in new rural cultural construction. The project assists in incorporating cultural change with the economic and social development to form symbiotic and culturally rich villages. The findings of the study may be utilised in the other rural areas that require formulating their cultural capital in the process of the sustainable development.

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